

INTEGRATION OF HOSPITAL PEDAGOGY AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article examines the importance of integrating hospital pedagogy and innovative technologies in improving the professional training of future teachers. The purpose of the study is to develop a model for developing digital and pedagogical competencies necessary for future teachers to work with children undergoing long-term treatment in hospital settings. The research used methods of pedagogical modeling, questionnaires among students, and comparative analysis of the experience of the "Mehrli Maktab" hospital schools. Innovative technologies in hospital pedagogy serve not only as a means of education, but also as a key factor in the social rehabilitation of students-patients.*

Keywords: *methodology, hospital pedagogy, innovative technology, education, hospital, modeling, questionnaire, integration, professional training, model.*

INTRODUCTION

In the modern global space, the amount of information received by individuals is rapidly changing. Therefore, in teaching inclusive education and hospital pedagogy, it is important to explore new opportunities through new methods, to strive not only to acquire simple knowledge, but also to understand the unexplored aspects of working with children with special educational needs. There is a growing need for future teachers who can implement an inclusive approach and abandon outdated pedagogical models, who can at the same time be a source of advice and inspiration. To meet these new requirements, future teachers must use and take into account modern innovative methods in accordance with the widely recognized principles of inclusive education.

The main goal of modern education is to prepare a person who is comprehensively developed for society and the state, socially adaptable to society and labor activity, and able to work on himself. As the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, emphasized, "it is an undeniable fact that the solution of the most urgent problems of society by highly qualified specialists depends on their professional knowledge, professional competence, high skills, rich spiritual and moral image, and cultural level"[1].

In order to ensure continuous education for children undergoing hematology, oncology, clinical immunology, and other inpatient and long-term outpatient treatment, in accordance with Resolution No. 234 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 2022 "On measures to introduce a system of preschool education and upbringing and general secondary education for children undergoing hematology, oncology, clinical immunology, and other inpatient and long-term outpatient treatment", on May 16, 2022, the "Mehrli Maktab" state educational institution, i.e. a hospital school, was established under the Ministry of Preschool and School Education.

METHODS

Issues of improving the methodological training of future teachers B.S.Abdullaeva[2], A.A.Abdukodirov, R.G.Isyanov, N.Muslimov[3], A.Kholikovlar; Research on improving the methodology for developing the professional training of future teachers in the CIS countries was conducted by G.T.Abdullina, O.V.Bakhtina, N.N.Golovina, N.P.Goncharuk, S.A.Lapteva, R.S.Nemov, J.Piaget, S.L.Rubenstein, Z.V.Sizensova, M.A.Kholodnaya.

Foreign scientists R.K.Blank, Marshal Cavendish, H.B. Gozalez, and Pavneet Kaur Bharaj conducted research on improving the methodology for developing the intellectual skills of future primary school teachers.

Researcher Q.M. Abdullayeva in her work “developed the structural structure of the individuality of a teacher at the stage of preparing future teachers for the profession. The developed structure identified intellectual, motivational, emotional, self-management,[4] practical subjective and volitional factors that affect the formation of professional competencies of a future teacher. Among them, the intellectual factor was the acquisition of problem-based educational skills, creativity and systematic thinking.

Foreign scientists Yamburg Ye.A., Sharikov S.V., Babenkova Ye.A., Gryadunova G.M., Kiseleva M.G., Amaleeva M.Yu., M. Dikson, M. Papadimitru, D. Steel, Ya. Haverkats contributed to the study of the problems of hospital pedagogy. The problems of rehabilitation of children with oncological diseases are addressed in the works of Volkova A.G., Volodin N.N., Maschan A.A., Rumyantsev A.G., Rudneva A.E., Sidorenko L.V., Seytlin G.Ya. Hospital pedagogy declares the implementation of the individual educational needs of a child with a long and serious illness as the highest value in education and sets the main task of forming a full-fledged educational environment in a medical inpatient setting to ensure the pedagogical rehabilitation of children with a long and serious illness.

Currently, large-scale reforms are being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to modernize the education system, in particular, to radically restructure the pedagogical education system and improve the quality of professional training of teachers. One of the important areas of these reforms is the development of inclusive education and the integration of knowledge and skills in the field of hospital pedagogy into the teacher training system. At the same time, the issues of applying hospital pedagogy methods in the educational process, studying them theoretically and applying them in practice by higher pedagogical educational institutions have not been sufficiently studied and are practically not used in practice. The fact that hospital pedagogy is not taught as a separate course in many pedagogical universities, and the limited opportunities for students to conduct pedagogical practice in hospital conditions are among the main problems in this area.

This situation indicates the need to update, improve and widely introduce methods for developing professional competencies of future teachers based on the best practices of hospital pedagogy, innovative approaches and modern technologies. Especially in today's era, when the principles of inclusive education are widely implemented, the training of future teachers in accordance with the foundations of hospital pedagogy, the formation of special competencies necessary for working with children with health problems, is of urgent scientific and practical importance.

Professional competence is a multifaceted and multifaceted concept, which changes in accordance with the changes taking place in society and is viewed from different points of view. An analysis of modern approaches to the content of the concept of "professional competence" of a teacher shows that this problem is currently being actively studied by domestic and foreign scientists, who give different meanings to its interpretation. Ye.V. Bondarevskaya connects the

concept of professional competence with the concept of "pedagogical culture", which is considered its main component and helps to form not a "craftsman in education", but a highly cultured specialist.

The research conducted by A. Kostyk and M. Oliynyk (2024) is devoted to an in-depth study of the possibilities of using innovative technologies in the professional activities of speech therapists. During these studies, it was proven that the main purpose of such technologies, especially in the context of inclusive education and hospital pedagogy, is to further improve correctional and developmental work with children with special needs, including those with health problems and requiring long-term treatment, to expand their educational opportunities and accelerate their social adaptation. It was found that these innovative technologies, when used in combination with traditional technologies, give more effective results in overcoming speech disorders in preschool children, in particular, in children receiving treatment in hospital settings or in inclusive education groups. These traditional technologies include fairy tale therapy (dramatizing fairy tales, correcting and improving children's emotional state through role-playing), art therapy (healing through creativity and creating opportunities for self-expression), aesthetic therapy (affecting personal development through the visual arts), and many other methods.

RESULTS

Within the framework of this scientific research, the following methods were used to determine the importance of innovative methods in teaching inclusive education and hospital pedagogy in improving the professional qualifications of future teachers:

1. Theoretical methods - generalization of best practices in professional training of future teachers in inclusive education and hospital pedagogy, creation of new technologies and methods for the formation of professional potential of future specialists in inclusive and hospital pedagogy through analysis, synthesis and organization of special literature and psychological and pedagogical sources, as well as clarification of the meaning and essence of the concepts of "inclusive competence", "hospital pedagogy", "innovative approach".

2. Practical methods - observation of pedagogical processes in inclusive educational institutions and hospital schools, conducting questionnaires among professors, teachers, practicing specialists and students, pedagogical experiment-testing to check the effectiveness of the developed pedagogical conditions (creating an inclusive educational environment, harmonizing hospital pedagogical methods), assessing the level of knowledge of future teachers on inclusive and hospital pedagogy through test tasks, studying the practice of working with children studying in a hospital setting (case study) and expert assessment.

3. Mathematical and statistical methods - correlation analysis to determine the numerical relationships between situations and process the collected data during the study, and verify the reliability of the results of pedagogical experiment-testing.

Inklyuziv ta'lim va gospital pedagogika sharoitida bo'lajak pedagogning samarali faoliyati uchun asosiy vazifalarni ajratib ko'rsatish:

- apply innovative technologies in creating personalized learning trajectories for children with special educational needs and students recovering in a hospital setting;
- have in-depth knowledge of innovative technologies (for example, distance learning platforms, specially adapted programs, therapeutic methods) that are effective in forming the professional qualifications of future teachers in inclusive and hospital pedagogy;
- be able to combine innovative approaches with traditional methods in their professional activities, effectively use innovative methods of specialists with advanced experience in the field of inclusive education and hospital pedagogy;

- organize and support the educational process in accordance with the values of inclusive education (equality, respect, acceptance) and the principles of hospital pedagogy (individual approach, psychological support);
- introduction and improvement of innovative pedagogical technologies in working with children with health problems, including students who need long-term treatment;
- eliminate pedagogical problems that arise in inclusive educational institutions and hospital schools (for example, inability to attend classes due to a child's illness, mental difficulties);
- create a developing and comfortable educational environment for children with special needs and students in hospital settings using innovative didactic materials and specially adapted teaching aids;
- understand and apply methods for implementing non-traditional approaches and new ideas in the process of forming professional capacity for inclusive and hospital pedagogy through innovative technologies;
- encourage cooperation and a positive atmosphere in the inclusive education team and the hospital pedagogical team, establish effective cooperation with various specialists (doctors, psychologists, defectologists);
- ensure effective communication and cooperation with all participants in the educational process - parents (especially parents of sick children), children with special needs, healthy peers and other educators.

DISCUSSION

The integration of hospital pedagogy and innovative technologies in the development of professional training of future teachers in accordance with the requirements of the time is becoming particularly relevant today.

The main directions and significance of this integration can be considered in the following points:

1. Hospital pedagogy is aimed at ensuring the right to education of children undergoing long-term treatment. Preparing future teachers in this area forms in them not only the skills of teaching, but also psychological stability and rehabilitation approaches.

2. Traditional teaching methods in a hospital setting are not always effective. Therefore, the following technologies are used in integration:

Distance and hybrid education: Establishing communication through digital platforms (LMS, Zoom, Google Classroom) for students who are limited in their ability to leave the hospital ward.

- VR and AR (Virtual and Augmented Reality): Virtual organization of excursions or laboratory work to distract children from the hospital environment and increase their interest in the lesson.

- Gamification: Using educational games to reduce stress during the treatment process and maintain learning motivation.

3. The following innovations should be introduced in the training of future specialists:

- Modernization of curricula: Introduction of the subject "Hospital Pedagogy" in pedagogical universities and emphasis on the use of IT technologies in it.

- Emphasis on inclusivity: Teaching students the methodology of adapting textbooks to the health status of each child (adaptive curricula).

- Practical training: Organizing internships for students in schools directly affiliated with the hospital (such as the "Kind School" within the framework of the "Zamin" project).

4. Expected results of integration

- Adaptability: The teacher can work effectively in any non-standard situation (hospital, home education).
- Empathy and creativity: The teacher learns to creatively organize the lesson, taking into account the physical condition of the student.
- Digital literacy: The skill of subordinating complex technological tools to pedagogical goals is formed.

The synthesis of hospital pedagogy and innovations elevates the future teacher to the level of a "tutor-pedagogue" who is not just a provider of knowledge, but also contributes to the social adaptation of the child.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the study, the role of innovative approaches in teaching inclusive education and hospital pedagogy in developing the professional competence of future teachers was scientifically substantiated. It was determined that traditional teaching methods are insufficient for training qualified specialists in the field of inclusive education and hospital pedagogy, therefore, the importance of introducing innovative technologies was highlighted. Hospital pedagogy plays an important role in the formation of such important competencies in future teachers as empathy, flexibility, mental endurance, and a personal approach. Although attention is paid to inclusive education in Uzbekistan, there is little research on hospital pedagogy, the subject is not taught as an independent course, and there are insufficient opportunities for practice. Innovative approaches such as information technologies, case methods, problem-based learning, game and project methods serve to form the practical skills of students. International experience confirms the effectiveness of digital technologies in this area. In conclusion, it can be said that it is necessary to establish hospital pedagogy as an independent course in Uzbekistan, expand students' opportunities for internships in hospital settings, and widely introduce innovative technologies into the educational process.

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